

EVALUATING DATA SECURITY MEASURES IN THE FIVE EYES ALLIANCE: A
FOCUS ON NEW ZEALAND GOVERNMENT MINISTRIES' ELECTRONIC
RECORD MANAGEMENT

BY

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AUTHORSHIP STATEMENT

I, Nicola Miller-Clendon, attest that the work in this thesis is substantially my own.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	iii
AUTHORSHIP STATEMENT	iv
LIST OF ACRONYMS	vii
ABSTRACT	x
CHAPTER	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background and Context	1
1.2 Current Research.....	1
1.3 Conceptualising Privacy in relation to Personal Information.....	6
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	8
2.1 The rationale for collaboration within the Five Eyes Alliance	9
2.2 Privacy law relating to Personal information.....	10
2.3 Case Studies within New Zealand Government Ministries	25
2.4 Case Studies within Five Eyes Alliance Nations.....	36
3. CRITICAL ANALYSIS	46
4. CONCLUSION	54
4.1 Summary of findings.....	54
4.2 Recommendations.....	55
BIBLIOGRAPHY	57

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
APP	Australian Privacy Principles
EU	European Union
ICO	Information Commissioner's Office
IPP	Information Privacy Principle
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OAIC	Office of the Australian Information Commissioner
OPC	Office of the Privacy Commissioner
UK	The United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
US	The United States of America

ABSTRACT

This thesis explores the protection of personal information under the electronic record management strategies and processes of New Zealand Government Ministries as governed by the Privacy Act 2020 from the perspective of New Zealand within the ‘Five Eyes’ Alliance, specifically focusing on immigration-related data shared among member states. The study considers legislative frameworks, geopolitical conflicts, case studies, and emerging technologies to provide a comprehensive analysis of the complexities surrounding digital sovereignty and privacy while complying with the information sharing arrangement. A critical examination of the most relevant, recent, and scholarly materials was carried using key search terms to allow a comparative analysis of the relevant legislation in each of the alliance member States. This research identified gaps, strengths, weaknesses, and controversies in the current understanding of data security measures within associated Government Ministries and within the alliance.

Keywords: Government; New Zealand; Five Eyes; Privacy; Policies; Australia; Canada; United Kingdom; United States

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Context:

Since 9/11 terror-related activity performed by non-state actors such as political militias, criminal, and international terrorist groups has become an even greater major concern¹. The United Nations has deemed terrorism a chief concern in their global agenda, urging member states to work towards achieving a world free from terrorism by adapting and innovating. The “promotion of multilateral cooperation” is at the centre of UN Office of Counter Terrorism’s work².

The ‘Five Eyes’ is a multilateral intelligence-sharing arrangement comprising of the major intelligence services of Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States³. A Memorandum of Understanding has been signed between five nations in the form of a statement of intent⁴ and specific guidelines exist with regard to the sharing of biometric data by the Migration 5, subgroup of the ‘Five Eyes’⁵ in order to facilitate the sharing of information and guidelines regarding the extent to which this information may be shared within the member countries.

¹ United Nations A New Era of Conflict and Violence

² UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy A/RES/60/288 (2006)

³ Brad Williams “Why the Five Eyes? Power and Identity in the Formation of a Multilateral Intelligence Grouping” (2023)

⁴ Statement of Intent among the Partners of the Migration Five (M5) for Notification regarding Bilateral Secure Real-Time Platform Activity

⁵ Biometric data-sharing process (Migration 5 biometric data-sharing process)

The protection of personal information within the electronic record management strategies and processes of New Zealand Government Ministries, governed by the Privacy Act 2020, holds paramount importance within the context of the 'Five Eyes' Alliance. When focusing specifically on immigration-related data shared among member states, the Privacy Act 2020 provides a robust legislative framework to safeguard individual privacy while participating in intelligence-sharing initiatives.

In New Zealand, the Privacy Act 2020 meticulously outlines the principles and guidelines for the collection, storage, and sharing of personal information. These provisions extend to electronic record management within government ministries, emphasizing a transparency, accountability, and adherence to ethical standards. The Act ensures that information, especially in sensitive areas like immigration, is handled with utmost care, respecting the rights of individuals and protecting against unwarranted intrusion.

Within the 'Five Eyes' Alliance, the shared commitment to treating information safely is reflected in each member state's adherence to its own legislative frameworks. For instance, in the United States, the Privacy Act of 1974 places restrictions on the collection and dissemination of personal information held by federal agencies. Similarly, Canada's Privacy Act of 1985 and the United Kingdom's Data Protection, Privacy, and Electronic Communications Regulations contribute to a comprehensive approach to information protection.

In conclusion, the post-9/11 era has necessitated a paradigm shift in the way nations approach security. The 'Five Eyes' alliance, rooted in multilateral cooperation, exemplifies

an effective model for addressing the complex and dynamic challenges posed by terrorism. As nations continue to innovate and adapt, the alliance stands as a testament to the collective strength that can be harnessed when nations work together towards a common goal.

It is crucial to consider how various legislative frameworks, emerging technologies, and ethical considerations play a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of intelligence sharing and data security. These elements provide a broader context for understanding the complexities and challenges faced by nations committed to ensuring global security and countering terrorism.

1.1.1. Legislative Frameworks

The legislative frameworks governing national security and intelligence activities form the bedrock upon which the 'Five Eyes' alliance operates. Each member state contributes to a collective understanding of the legal parameters within which intelligence sharing occurs. The purview of legislation, such as the Homeland Security Act in the United States, the Privacy Act in Canada, and New Zealand's Privacy Act, serves as a lens through which the alliance navigates the delicate balance between safeguarding national security and upholding individual rights and privacy. Retaining a strong sense of the protection of personal information, even when shared between nations is paramount.

1.1.2. Emerging Technologies:

The rapid evolution of technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, introduces new dimensions to both intelligence gathering and data security. The alliance must grapple with the implications of these technologies on the effectiveness of counter-

terrorism efforts on a global level and data security on a national level. Consideration of technological advancements becomes paramount in evaluating the alliance's resilience against emerging threats. Addressing the potential impact of these technologies, both in terms of opportunities and challenges, becomes a critical aspect of shaping future strategies within the 'Five Eyes' alliance.

1.1.3. Ethical Considerations:

The ethical dimensions of intelligence sharing, and data security are integral to maintaining public trust and ensuring responsible governance. As the alliance harnesses the power of information, questions arise regarding data ownership, consent, and accountability. Examining ethical frameworks becomes essential in understanding the societal implications of intelligence operations. Additionally, cultural, and societal norms play a role in shaping perceptions of privacy, necessitating a nuanced approach to ethical considerations within the alliance.

Understanding how legislative frameworks, emerging technologies, and ethical considerations intersect with the collaborative efforts of the 'Five Eyes' alliance enriches the analysis of each's nations' effectiveness. An ongoing dialogue and adaptation within the alliance to address these multifaceted challenges should underscore that the commitment to not only thwarting immediate threats but also upholding the principles of transparency, accountability, and respect for individual rights in an ever-evolving security landscape.

The New Zealand Public are naturally concerned that their personal information be kept secure and only shared with 'Five Eyes' Alliance Partners as is necessary. To ensure that

they feel confident of this New Zealand needs to be in absolute certainty that not only is that information gathered, used, and stored or protected in a way that meets the requirements of the Privacy Act 2020 but any information which is shared offshore is protected in the same manner. Concerns are raised when Government Departments who may not be key agencies sharing data with 'Five Eyes' alliance agencies but whose data is still shared on some levels are hit by cyberattacks. However, there may be greater cause for concern regarding a large number of preventable data breaches occurring within these agencies, particularly through human error.

1.2 Current Research:

Accordingly, this research aims systematically review and compare New Zealand's current privacy framework to legislation employed by alliance countries. The focus of this comparative policy analysis will be on protection of personal information under legislation implemented by members of the 'Five Eyes' alliance. Confining this analysis to the 'Five Eyes' alliance is suitable for reasons beyond their joint membership within an alliance dedicated to maintaining national security. All nations share a common legal heritage and to a certain extent political process, being a democratic election of representatives to govern.

The analysis will examine practices the electronic record management strategies and processes within government agencies and evaluate divergent government responses to the importance of protection of personal information when balanced against the requirements of national security and the collection, storage and sharing of information between member states. With these goals in mind, the analysis will first review theoretical frameworks and

perspectives for understanding the possible differing goals of protection of personal information. Secondly, comparative case studies in the form of a literature review will be evaluated to identify similarities and differences and common themes. Strengths and weaknesses identified will be discussed. Finally, recommendations for improvements in protection of personal information, recommendations for Government agencies in the reduction of threats to personal information as well as data and for further study will be provided. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to ongoing improvements to the protection of personal information.

1.3 Conceptualising Privacy in relation to Personal Information:

The term ‘privacy’ can be conceptualised in a variety of ways, particularly when it is relating to personal information, with differing definitions being in evidence across each alliance nation^{6 7 8}. Understandably political, economic, legislative, and societal factors influence the reasons for these differences. However, the member states of the ‘Five Eyes’ Alliance all seem to have similar concepts of privacy of personal information but how it is entrenched in legislation varies. According to most data privacy laws, personal information is any information that can be used to identify a person.

The legislation governing the protection of private information in each country are as follows:

⁶ Bellman, Johnson, Kobrin & Lohse “International Differences in Information Privacy Concerns: A Global Survey of Consumers”

⁷ Westin, A. F. (2003). “Social and Political Dimensions of Privacy”

⁸ Whitman, James Q. "The Two Western Cultures of Privacy: Dignity versus Liberty" at [1160]

Australia: Privacy Act 1988 – Australian Privacy Principles

Canada: Privacy Act 1985, Personal Information Protection and Electronic

Documents Act

New Zealand: Privacy Act 2020

United Kingdom: Data Protection Act 2018

United States: The Privacy Act 1974 which applies to information about individuals that is held by federal agencies.

California: California Consumer Privacy Act, California Privacy Rights Act, California Online Privacy Protection Act

Virginia: Consumer Data Protection Act

Colorado: Colorado Privacy Act

Connecticut: Connecticut Personal Data Privacy and Online Monitoring Act

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review found no existing case studies related to the protection of personal information as a comparison between 'Five Eyes' member states. It therefore explores existing studies relating to individual member states and legislative frameworks, including current laws governing data collection and sharing within each member state.

The exchanging of data both between New Zealand Government entities and between the 'Five Eyes', the intelligence alliance between New Zealand and the US, Canada, UK, and Australia, creates challenges to ensuring that the privacy, confidentiality, and security of this data is maintained where each country is governed by their own legislation regarding privacy and their own policies and guidelines regarding the implementation of this legislation. This issue has been highlighted by not only recent public sector privacy and security breaches in New Zealand but by breaches in security in all four other countries including the US Department of Homeland Security, the Department of Home Affairs in Australia and the National Security and Intelligence Review Agency in Canada which all hold records shared with and received from New Zealand Government agencies. This raises concerns about systemic issues within the countries participating in the Five Country Ministerial regarding the security and protection of personal information both belonging to and regarding individuals obtained by these agencies and shared between these agencies, and a possible disconnect between strategy and implementation of data security within these agencies.

The collaborative efforts within the 'Five Eyes' Alliance hinge on the trust that member states place in one another's ability to handle and secure sensitive data. Ensuring alignment

with relevant legislation, will result in each member state contributing to a collective commitment to uphold the highest standards of privacy and data security. This legislative synergy acts as a cornerstone in fostering mutual trust and maintaining the integrity of intelligence-sharing processes within the alliance, particularly where it relates to immigration.

2.1 The rationale for collaboration within the 'Five Eyes' Alliance:

The nations of the 'Five Eyes' alliance share a close commonality of backgrounds which make both the sharing of information to reduce the risk of terror attacks and reaching similar guidelines regarding the protection of personal information potentially easier to achieve than in alliances where member nations come from disparate political, socio-legal and belief-based backgrounds.

Beyond legal frameworks, the alliance has also recognized the significance of responsible information-sharing, particularly in the realm of biometric data. Biometric information is defined as "*information about an individual's biological or behavioural characteristics: for example, a facial image, a fingerprint pattern or a digital template of that image or pattern*"⁹. The Migration 5 subgroup's specific guidelines on biometric data-sharing highlight the alliance's commitment to safeguarding sensitive information^{10 11}. These

⁹ Biometrics and Privacy – the Office of the Privacy Commissioner

¹⁰ Statement of Intent among the Partners of the Migration Five (M5) for Notification regarding Bilateral Secure Real-Time Platform Activity

¹¹ Biometric data-sharing process (Migration 5 biometric data-sharing process)

guidelines not only facilitate effective information exchange but also establish a framework for accountability and transparency, vital components in maintaining public trust and international collaboration.

The 'Five Eyes' underscore the belief that through collaborative endeavors, nations can harness the power of shared knowledge and resources to stay one step ahead of emerging threats.

2.2 Privacy law relating to Personal information:

2.2.1 Australia:

In Australia, the protection of personal information can be considered to be a cornerstone of the nation's commitment to individual privacy and data security. The legislative landscape, led by the Privacy Act 1988, serves as a robust framework that regulates how personal information is collected, used, stored, and disclosed by both government agencies and private sector organizations. It is important to examine key aspects of Australian legislation and associated policies that collectively contribute to a comprehensive privacy protection regime.

Privacy Act 1988 and Australian Privacy Principles (APPs):

The Privacy Act 1988 forms the bedrock of Australia's privacy protection framework. Its overarching objective is to ensure that individuals have confidence in the way their personal information is handled by organizations. At the heart of the Privacy Act are the Australian Privacy Principles (APPs), a set of guidelines that prescribe how entities subject to the Act must manage personal information. The APPs cover critical aspects, including

the open and transparent management of data, the right to anonymity, and the secure handling of sensitive information. Crucially, the Privacy Act applies to a broad spectrum of entities, incorporating government agencies and private sector organizations with an annual turnover above a specified threshold. This broad scope underscores the commitment to fostering a culture of privacy awareness across various sectors of the Australian economy.

Notifiable Data Breaches (NDB) Scheme:

The introduction of the Notifiable Data Breaches (NDB) scheme in 2018 marked a pivotal moment in Australia's approach to data security¹². An amendment to the Privacy Act, the NDB scheme mandates organisations covered by the Act to notify both affected individuals and the Office of the Australian Information Commissioner (OAIC) in the event of a significant data breach. This proactive measure enhances transparency and accountability, ensuring that individuals are promptly informed about breaches that may compromise their personal information.

My Health Records Act 2012:

Within healthcare, the My Health Records Act 2012 governs the creation and management of the My Health Record system. This legislation underscores the sensitivity of health-related information and grants individuals control over their health records. By defining who can access and manage this data, the My Health Records Act aligns with broader privacy principles, contributing to a robust protection framework for personal health information.

Telecommunications (Interception and Access) Act 1979:

¹² Office of the Australian Information Commissioner “About the Notifiable Data Breaches scheme

While primarily focused on law enforcement interception of communications, the Telecommunications (Interception and Access) Act 1979 however acknowledges the need for strict controls and oversight to safeguard individuals' privacy. The balance between the imperative for public safety with the protection of privacy rights in this legislation reflects a nuanced approach to regulating the interception of communications in Australia.

Australian Government Agencies Privacy Code:

The Australian Government Agencies Privacy Code was introduced in 2018 and serves to strengthen privacy protections within government agencies. Aligned with the Australian Privacy Principles, this code outlines specific requirements and practices that government entities must adhere to. By setting clear expectations for responsible and transparent data handling, the code enhances public trust in government agencies' management of personal information.

Other relevant Policies and Future Considerations:

In addition to legislative frameworks, various policies complement Australia's privacy laws, offering practical guidance to organizations and agencies. The Privacy Management Framework¹³, developed by the Australian Government, provides a structured approach to embedding privacy considerations into organizational practices. Moreover, sector-specific guidelines, such as those for the health and telecommunications sectors, offer tailored insights into privacy compliance within specialized contexts.

¹³ Office of the Australian Information Commissioner “Privacy management framework: enabling compliance and encouraging good practice”

Consideration of issues such as data portability, artificial intelligence, and cross-border data flows will be pivotal in shaping the future trajectory of privacy protection in Australia. Australia's legislative and policy framework for the protection of personal information appears to reflect a comprehensive commitment to individual privacy rights. The multifaceted approach, encompassing legislation, principles, and sector-specific guidelines, establishes a robust foundation for responsible and transparent data management.

2.2.2 Canada:

Canada appears to place a paramount emphasis on safeguarding the privacy and personal information of its citizens, a commitment reflected in its robust legislative framework and associated policies.

Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA):

At the forefront of Canada's privacy protection landscape stands the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA). Enacted in 2000, PIPEDA regulates the collection, use, and disclosure of personal information by private-sector organisations engaged in commercial activities. PIPEDA ensures that organisations subject to its provisions adhere to fair information practices, emphasizing transparency, accountability, and consent. A foundational element of PIPEDA is the ten principles outlined in the Canadian Standards Association's Model Code for the Protection of Personal Information. These principles form the core of the Act, governing aspects such as accountability, consent, and the right of individuals to access their personal information.

Digital Privacy Act and Amendments to PIPEDA:

The Digital Privacy Act, which came into force in 2015, introduced significant amendments to PIPEDA, enhancing the Act's effectiveness in addressing evolving privacy challenges. Key amendments include mandatory breach reporting, ensuring that organizations promptly notify individuals and the Office of the Privacy Commissioner of security breaches that pose a risk of significant harm¹⁴. This proactive measure bolsters transparency and empowers individuals to take steps to protect themselves in the aftermath of a data breach.

Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms:

While not exclusively focused on privacy of personal information, the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms underpins the broader legal framework within which privacy rights are situated. Section 8 of the Charter protects individuals against unreasonable search and seizure, providing a constitutional foundation for privacy rights in Canada. The Charter serves as a backdrop against which privacy legislation is interpreted, ensuring a harmonious relationship between privacy protection and other fundamental rights.

Sectoral Legislation:

In addition to PIPEDA, Canada has sector-specific legislation that addresses privacy concerns in particular industries. For instance, the Personal Health Information Protection Act (PHIPA) in Ontario governs the protection of health-related information. This sectoral approach recognizes the unique privacy considerations associated with specific domains, tailoring legislation to address the requirements of different sectors.

¹⁴ Data Protection Report “Canada amends federal data protection law, PIPEDA”.

Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada (OPC):

The Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada (OPC) serves as the independent oversight body responsible for ensuring compliance with PIPEDA¹⁵. Endowed with investigative and enforcement powers, the OPC plays a crucial role in upholding privacy rights and promoting awareness about privacy issues. The Commissioner investigates complaints, conducts audits, and provides guidance to organizations on privacy best practices. The OPC issues policy statements and guidelines that interpret and apply privacy principles in various contexts. These policies contribute to a nuanced understanding of how privacy laws should be implemented and adhered to in real-world scenarios.

Canada's commitment to privacy protection appears evident in its well-established legislative framework and associated policies. PIPEDA, with its foundational principles, serves as the cornerstone, augmented by sector-specific legislation and the amendments introduced through the Digital Privacy Act. The role of the OPC as an oversight body and educator reinforces the importance of privacy in Canadian society. The intersection of technology, constitutional rights, and international considerations underscores the need for a dynamic and responsive approach to privacy protection. In upholding the rights enshrined in PIPEDA and the broader legal framework, Canada ensures that its citizens can navigate the digital world with confidence in the protection of their personal information.

¹⁵ Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada “About the OPC “

2.2.3 New Zealand

New Zealand prioritises the protection of personal information, and this commitment is enshrined in a comprehensive legislative framework. In addition to legislation governing the protection of personal information, laws, principles, and policies all that collectively contribute to a robust privacy protection regime.

Privacy Act 2020:

At the core of New Zealand's privacy protection framework is the Privacy Act 2020. Enacted to modernize and enhance privacy protections set out in the previous Privacy Act, this legislation governs the collection, use, and disclosure of personal information by both government agencies and private sector organisations. The Privacy Act 2020 aligns with international best practices and reflects New Zealand's commitment to upholding individuals' privacy rights.

Key Principles of the Privacy Act 2020 are:

The Principle of Purpose whereby organisations must collect personal information for a lawful purpose connected with their activities and must not use it for any other purpose.

The Principle of Storage and Security whereby entities holding personal information must take reasonable steps to keep it secure and protect it from unauthorised access.

The Principle of Access and Correction under which individuals have the right to access their personal information held by organisations and request corrections if necessary.

The Principle of Agency whereby organisations must ensure that personal information is not disclosed to an agency outside New Zealand unless certain conditions are met. These principles are enshrined in the 13 Information Privacy Principles.

Notifiable Data Breaches:

The Privacy Act 2020 introduced mandatory data breach notification requirements, aligning New Zealand with global efforts to enhance transparency and accountability. Organisations are obligated to notify the Privacy Commissioner and affected individuals if a data breach poses a risk of harm. This proactive measure empowers individuals to take necessary actions to mitigate potential risks to their personal information.

Health Information Privacy Code:

Recognising the sensitivity of health-related data, New Zealand has a dedicated Health Information Privacy Code that operates in conjunction with the Privacy Act. This code provides additional safeguards for the collection, use, and disclosure of health information, ensuring that individuals' privacy is protected when accessing services within the healthcare sector.

The Office of the Privacy Commissioner (OPC):

The Privacy Commissioner is an independent authority established under the Privacy Act 2020. The OPC oversees compliance with privacy laws, handles complaints, and promotes awareness of privacy issues. The OPC plays a crucial role in ensuring that organisations adhere to the principles outlined in the Privacy Act 2020. The Privacy Commissioner issues guidelines and policies to assist organisations in understanding and complying with privacy obligations. These resources provide practical insights and best practices, contributing to a well-rounded contextual application of privacy principles.

New Zealand faces evolving challenges in the realm of privacy protection. The rapid pace of technological advancements, including artificial intelligence and data analytics, presents new complexities that require ongoing adaptation of privacy laws. Striking a balance between technological innovation and safeguarding personal information remains an

ongoing challenge. The Privacy Act 2020 was written to keep pace with international legislation and in consideration of international standards and frameworks. This ensures that its privacy laws align with broader global expectations, facilitating the seamless flow of information while upholding robust privacy protections.

The Privacy Act 2020, along with sector-specific codes, lays down principles that prioritize the fair and transparent handling of personal information. The role of the Privacy Commissioner and the introduction of mandatory data breach notification requirements demonstrate a commitment to proactive oversight and accountability.

2.2.4 United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom (UK), the protection of personal information forms a key part of its commitment to individual rights and privacy. The legislative framework governing this protection is strong, encompassing key regulations and acts that collectively create a resilient privacy protection regime.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

The advent of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) marked a paradigm shift in the protection of personal information in the United Kingdom. Enforceable since May 2018, GDPR was crafted to synchronise with data protection laws across the European Union (EU). Despite the UK's departure from the EU, the GDPR has been integrated into UK law relatively seamlessly, ensuring continuity and maintaining high standards for data protection. At its core, GDPR introduced fundamental principles, such as those seen within other nation's Privacy legislation, that guide the lawful processing of personal data. An emphasis on lawfulness, fairness, and transparency sets the tone for organisations to be clear and ethical in their data processing practices. Additional pillars to the Act are purpose

limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, and security to assist in fostering a culture of responsible and accountable data handling.

Data Protection Act 2018:

The Data Protection Act 2018 serves as a complementary piece of legislation to the GDPR by providing additional provisions and clarifications. It serves to address specific areas not covered by GDPR, such as the processing of personal data for law enforcement purposes and the activities of intelligence services. This act additionally empowers the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) to regulate and enforce data protection laws, acting in their role of guardian of privacy rights in the UK.

The Act further incorporates provisions related to individual rights, such as the right to access personal data, the right to erasure, and the right to object to processing. These rights empower individuals to have control over their personal information and ensure that organisations handle data in a way that respects individuals' autonomy.

Privacy and Electronic Communications Regulations (PECR):

Acting beyond general data protection, the Privacy and Electronic Communications Regulations (PECR) address specific privacy concerns related to electronic communications. Covering areas such as marketing communications, cookies, and the security of electronic communications services, PECR ensures that privacy rights are upheld in what is a rapidly evolving landscape of digital communication. It complements GDPR by offering targeted regulations tailored to the unique challenges posed by electronic communications.

Information Commissioner's Office (ICO):

As with other nations within the alliance, the UK has a commissioner responsible for privacy. The ICO plays a pivotal role as the UK's independent regulator for data protection and privacy. Empowered by GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018, the ICO oversees compliance with data protection laws, investigates reported breaches, and enforces penalties for non-compliance. The ICO's role also includes providing guidance to organisations and individuals to foster an awareness and understanding regarding data protection rights and responsibilities.

The ICO issues a plethora of policies and guidelines that interpret and provide practical insights into the application of data protection laws. These resources cater to the diverse challenges faced by organisations, offering advice on issues ranging from lawful processing to data subject rights to ensure that organisations have the necessary tools to navigate complex privacy scenarios, meet compliance requirements and handle data ethically.

Brexit introduced an additional layer of complexity, necessitating careful considerations in the UK's positioning within the global data protection landscape. Negotiating data flows with the EU while maintaining robust privacy standards domestically requires adept policymaking and a willingness towards international collaboration.

The integration of GDPR, the Data Protection Act 2018, and PECR has created what can be described as a harmonious and multifaceted approach to privacy protection.

2.2.5 United States

The protection of personal information in the United States is governed by a complex web of legislation, marked by federal, state, and sector-specific regulations. While certain laws

have been pivotal in safeguarding specific categories of personal data, the overall landscape lacks a comprehensive federal privacy law, leading to inadequacies and challenges in addressing the evolving needs of privacy in the digital age.

The Privacy Act of 1974:

The Privacy Act of 1974 was a landmark piece of legislation that aimed to curb the government's collection and handling of personal information. Enacted against the backdrop of concerns about government surveillance and data misuse, the Privacy Act established principles for federal agencies to follow when handling personal information. However, the Act has a number of limitations:

Scope and Applicability: The Privacy Act primarily applies to federal agencies, leaving significant gaps in the regulation of private-sector entities. As the digital ecosystem expanded, private entities became major custodians of personal data, and the Privacy Act failed to address their practices adequately.

Reaction to Technological Advancements: The act was enacted in an era vastly different from today's technologically advanced landscape. The rise of the internet, social media, and sophisticated data analytics has outpaced the regulatory framework established by the Privacy Act, rendering it insufficient to address many contemporary privacy challenges.

Lack of Comprehensive Rights for Individuals: While the Privacy Act grants individuals the right to access their records and seek corrections, it lacks comprehensive rights comparable to more modern privacy laws of other alliance nations. Concepts like the right to be forgotten, data portability, and comprehensive opt-in and opt-out mechanisms, which are integral in many contemporary privacy frameworks, are notably absent.

Fragmentation and Sector-Specific Regulations:

The absence of a comprehensive federal privacy law has led to a patchwork of regulations and laws governing specific sectors and types of data. This fragmentation creates challenges in providing consistent and robust privacy protections across the board.

Examples of Sector-Specific Regulations:

Health Data (HIPAA): The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) provides crucial protections for health-related personal information. However, its focus is intentionally narrow, leaving other types of personal data outside its purview.

Financial Data (GLBA): The Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act (GLBA) regulates the protection of nonpublic personal information held by financial institutions. While vital for the financial sector, it does nothing to address broader privacy concerns.

State-Level Initiatives:

In the absence of federal leadership, some states have taken it upon themselves to enact privacy regulations, leading to a complex landscape with varying standards. While states like California and Virginia have introduced comprehensive laws (CCPA and VCDPA), this approach raises concerns about inconsistency and compliance challenges for businesses operating across state lines.

Limitations of State-Level Initiatives:

Divergent Standards: The differing standards across states create compliance challenges, especially for businesses that operate nationally or globally. Harmonizing these standards is a critical task for creating a cohesive and effective privacy framework.

Potential Gaps: State laws may not cover all aspects of privacy protection or may leave certain sectors without adequate regulation. This can result in gaps that leave certain types of personal information less protected than others.

Proposed Federal Legislation and Ongoing Challenges:

Efforts to introduce a comprehensive federal privacy law have faced challenges in achieving consensus on the scope, enforcement mechanisms, and individual rights. Multiple bills, such as Consumer Online Privacy Rights Act (COPRA) and the Data Protection Act, have been proposed, reflecting the growing recognition of the need for a unified approach. However, these initiatives have faced hurdles in navigating political dynamics, industry interests, and divergent views on the balance between privacy and innovation.

Challenges which exist in Crafting Federal Legislation include:

The scope of application in as such as deciding which entities fall under the purview of a federal privacy law, especially concerning smaller businesses and emerging technologies, is a complex challenge that requires careful consideration.

Determining the appropriate enforcement mechanisms, penalties for non-compliance, and the role of regulatory bodies such as the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) require solutions which will ensure both effectiveness and fairness occur.

Striking a balance between empowering individuals with robust privacy rights and providing flexibility for businesses to innovate poses a challenge in crafting legislation that satisfies these diverse stakeholders.

International Considerations and Global Data Flows:

The global nature of data flows and international data transfer considerations further complicate the U.S. privacy landscape. The invalidation of the EU-U.S. Privacy Shield by the European Court of Justice on July 16, 2020¹⁶, highlighted the need for the U.S. to align

¹⁶ Gesley, Jenny “European Union: Court of Justice Invalidates US-EU Privacy Shield

its privacy standards with global expectations, emphasising the urgency of addressing inadequacies in its current framework.

Further Global Implications:

Negotiating Data Transfers: The U.S. must navigate international negotiations to establish frameworks that facilitate the lawful transfer of personal data across borders. This requires aligning with global standards, addressing concerns about government surveillance, and ensuring a level of protection equivalent to that provided in the European Union.

Addressing the inadequacies in U.S. privacy protection requires a multifaceted approach that combines legislative action, regulatory guidance, and international collaboration.

The U.S. needs to prioritise the enactment of comprehensive federal privacy legislation that establishes a unified framework applicable to both government and private entities. This legislation should incorporate modern privacy principles, individual rights, and flexible mechanisms to adapt to technological advancements. Efforts also need to be made to harmonize state-level privacy laws to ensure a consistent and coherent approach across the nation. This should involve establishing a baseline of privacy protections that states can build upon to address specific needs. Proactive Regulatory Oversight is needed, and it has been suggested that Regulatory bodies, such as the FTC, should play a more proactive role in overseeing privacy practices, enforcing compliance, and providing guidance to businesses and consumers in lieu of a dedicated independent Privacy Commissioner.

There also exists the need for increased public awareness about privacy rights, data practices, and the importance of informed consent through educational campaigns to empower individuals to make informed choices about their personal information.

The inadequacies of the Privacy Act of 1974 and the absence of a comprehensive federal privacy law leave the U.S. navigating a complex terrain of privacy protection.

2.3 Case Studies within New Zealand Government Ministries:

The Office of the Privacy Commissioner in a media release in January 2023 stated that there is also a slight increase in the percentage of serious breaches caused by malicious activity; however, the majority of breaches are caused by human error, most commonly email error and unauthorized sharing¹⁷. These are overall breaches but show a general pattern which appears to be applicable to Government agencies, particularly given that the most serious breaches reported are primarily in Health Care & Social Assistance and Public Administration & Safety¹⁸.

Mercury IT ransomware attack: The Ministry of Justice and Te Whatu Ora (Health New Zealand) reported being impacted by the cyberattack on third-party IT support provider, Mercury IT in November 2022. This attack did not result in any privacy breaches for these agencies but prevented access to files relating to the access of deceased persons' bodies and post-mortem examinations from March 2020 to date for the Ministry of Justice¹⁹. Te Whatu Ora had its access to bereavement and cardiac services impacted²⁰.

Stats NZ Tatauranga Aotearoa: Stats NZ is responsible for the Integrated Data Infrastructure (IDI) which links data received from Government agencies as well as from

¹⁷ Notable increase in data breaches reported. (Office of the Privacy Commissioner, 12 January 2023)

¹⁸ Office of the Privacy Commissioner

¹⁹ Statement – Cyber security incident. (Ministry of Justice, 18 January 2023) media release

²⁰ Cyber security incident impacting access to data. (Te Whatu Ora, 6 December 2022)

Stats NZ surveys and NGOs to create integrated data²¹. The data is according to the Stats NZ website de-identified. Researchers use the IDI for research, generally in the interest of improving outcomes for New Zealanders. Their website states that they check research results before they're released to make sure individuals can't be identified. In February of 2023 Stuff NZ disclosed that this database had had its rules breached more than 100 times²². Since 2015 there have been 103 policy breaches since 2015 and 79 of those have been since 2019 and November 2022. Researchers most frequently failed to round data to the closest multiple of three – random rounding to base 3²³, which is a practice in place to specifically protect privacy in the cases of small counts. A breach with potentially more risk occurred where health data from people who did not consent to their information being linked were visible in IDI for a short period of time. Stats NZ considered these to be minor breaches which did not allow personal data to leave the Data Lab. However, another common breach identified was researchers sharing images they had taken from the IDI, usually to request help from Stats NZ staff members or other researchers (taking photos is prohibited)²⁴. These images could remain on their phones as images and therefore potentially would allow personal data to leave the Data Lab. Given that researchers must

²¹ Stats NZ website information on IDI

²² Stuff online article “Massive government database had rules breached more than 100 times.”.

²³ Stats NZ explains this method as all figures in the tables being randomly rounded where all counts are randomly rounded up or down to one of the adjoining multiples of three (eg a count of five is displayed as either 3 or 6, and a count of one is displayed as either 0 or 3). Counts under four are withheld

²⁴ Thomas Beagle requested and received the source data used in the Stuff article as an OIA request to Stats NZ in March 2018.

sign confidentiality agreements not to disclose any personal information they do see there must exist the potential for personal information to not be deidentified.

Ministry of Social Development: In October 2023 the Christchurch Press²⁵, in addition to other media outlets, reported that an email had been sent out to nearly 500 jobseekers with every recipient email address visible. The email was from the Papanui Christchurch branch of Work and Income and two recall requests were made, again sharing all email addresses with everyone that the original email was sent to. Finally, a request that the previous email containing sensitive information be deleted was sent out to a BCC list. Following on from this an abusive email was sent to all recipients from an anonymous sender whose email address did not appear on the addresses on the previous emails, pointing to further sharing of the email list.

In 2017 it was reported²⁶ that MSD had stored data collected about individual clients by NGOs in a Government Shared Workspace provided by the Department of Internal Affairs (DIA), using Microsoft SharePoint 2010, which by default, allows users to see everything within their workspace because it has been designed to be a collaboration tool. To prevent users from viewing or accessing materials they were not meant to, permissions for users were selectively removed from their default settings. It was intended that access was restricted to the NGO that had provided the information. MSD was advised that one NGO had been able to see a folder containing client information from another NGO as a result of an error in user permissions allocations. This was the first phase of the breach. In the second phase, while seeking to fix the problem by removing user permissions, the Ministry

²⁵ MSD data breach affects nearly 500 people

²⁶ NZ Herald report

had accidentally deleted its own user permissions. They then had to request that the service provider Datacom re-instate their access to that library. However, when the access was re-instated it was reinstated for all users which enabled all the NGOs to view that library. A review was undertaken and identified key errors, including not enough attention being paid to privacy during the program and the late completion of an impact assessment²⁷ and the Office of the Privacy Commissioner also released focused on MSD's collection of individual client-level data from NGOs²⁸.

Immigration New Zealand (INZ): As an agency that shares information with other members of the Five Eyes alliance under the umbrella of Migration Five, any breaches by this agency are of particular interest. Much literature retrieved related to breaches related to “whistle blowers” providing information to the media, including the use of a very low touch when assessing certain visa types²⁹ and the knock-on effect resulting in a spike in asylum claims from visitor visas with the view that New Zealand is a ‘soft touch’³⁰. The sometimes-extensive timeframe for processing these claims can allow claimants to work in New Zealand to work in New Zealand and receive other benefits. Where these asylum claims are not successful the claimants may still extend their time in New Zealand by appealing to the Immigration Protection Tribunal so being able to cross the border is an attractive proposition..

²⁷ An independent review of MSD's decisions relating to the IT system used to capture individual client level data was carried out by Murray Jack (FCA).

²⁸ The Privacy Commissioner made four recommendations with regards to their information collection practices.

²⁹ Kilgallon “Immigration staff tell of behind-the scenes visa dysfunction” (2023)

³⁰ Kilgallon “Spike in NZ refugee claims sees applications up by hundreds in one year” (2023)

However, release of personal information to third parties due to errors in data entry occurs with reasonable frequency. These often occur when a migrant changes advisor while an application is in process and the advisor tab of the database is not updated. INZ has a Visa Pak (information updates and guidance for employees) which deals with Privacy Breaches relating to data entry which specially states “Please ensure that all contact tabs are correctly updates with each new application”³¹. This is of a greater concern possibly in the Refugee & Migrant space because this space does not issue visas but assesses claims for Refugee or Protected Person status so claimants may provide a large amount of personal information to be assessed prior to interview but they or their advisor are also provided with a full file disclosure – that is all the files that INZ holds for the claimant - prior to interview. This may hold personal information including evidence for genuine partnership, transcripts of phone interviews providing sensitive information, any investigations into the claimant, active police charges or convictions. If the incorrect advisor is listed then this information will potentially be released to a third party who does not have authority to access this material. Data entry errors have also resulted in the providing of personal information belonging to one visa applicant to another unrelated applicant. In 2019, Immigration New Zealand staff breached privacy 170 times and 1232 times in the four years prior to 2020 according to an RNZ article ³²

A more concerning case of how INZ’s seemly small breaches of privacy principles may show a weakened position in its role in providing information to the Migration five was

³¹ Visa Pak 144. Information about Privacy Breach when officers fail to update adviser and email details correctly

³² Gill Bonnett “Privacy breaches at Immigration NZ: ‘We open up our whole lives to them’” RNZ (6 August 2020)

the case of an Ethiopian migrant who was unable to have his date of birth corrected despite medical and documentary evidence supporting his claim. His case was reported to the Office of the Privacy Commissioner who in turn referred the case to the Director of Human Rights Proceedings³³. The complainant had arrived in New Zealand with incorrect information on his travel documents. His correct birth date was unknown as birth registration is not compulsory in Ethiopia³⁴ and an estimated date in 2000, likely to be 01/Jan/2000, was placed on his documents based on discussion with members of his community. This information was taken at face value by INZ as is the common practice, identity documents are generally not queried unless there is reason for concern and verification with the Ethiopian Government would have shown that the documents were genuine. However, migrants are required to undergo a general medical examination if planning to stay in New Zealand or having remained in New Zealand for more than six months³⁵. According to case notes from the Office of the Privacy Commissioner³⁶, in carrying out this examination the Immigration New Zealand appointed panel physician advised INZ that the applicant appeared to be older than his date of birth suggested. This in itself should have raised concerns for INZ regarding the possibility of identity theft, however it does not appear to have done so. The complainant underwent a bone scan in 2012 and a dental examination in 2013 to clarify his age. Indications from both were that

³³ Commissioner finds Immigration NZ in breach (Office of the Privacy Commissioner, 18 August 2015)

³⁴ Abay, S. T., & Gebre-egziabher, A. G. "Status and associated factors of birth registration in selected districts of Tigray region, Ethiopia" (2020).

³⁵ Immigration New Zealand Operational Manual sA4.25 Medical and Chest X-ray Certificates: temporary entry class visa applications

³⁶ Office of the Privacy Commissioner Case note 264435[2015] NZ PrivCmr 8

his age was significantly older than his recorded age, making him between over 16 years old and possibly up to 18 years old. Given this age would allow the complainant legal entitlements including the ability to obtain a drivers license, financial assistance for study or job seeking, the complainant requested that INZ change his date of birth, but INZ refused. The complainant then obtained an amended birth certificate from Ethiopia in 2014 but INZ would not accept the birth certificate and again refused to change his birth certificate. At this point in time INZ was recording his age as 14 but other evidence showed that he was over 17 years old. INZ did offer to add a ‘correction requested but not granted’ note as under IPP 7(4)³⁷ to his client file but this would not have changed the complainant’s circumstances in any material manner. The complainant laid a complaint with the Office of the Privacy Commissioner. The Privacy Commissioner considered prior judgements from the Human Rights Review Tribunal to provide guidance. In *Jones v Waitemata District Health Board*, it was set out that if the agency considers, on reasonable grounds, that the existing data is correct, no changes need be made³⁸. However, the Commissioner was of the opinion that given the independent evidence provided INZ did not have reasonable grounds to believe that the birth date on file was correct. The Human Rights Review Tribunal advised in the case of *Henderson v Commissioner of Inland Revenue*³⁹ agencies do not always have a choice about whether to correct information, in certain cases the kind of information and its likely use, and the extent of the inaccuracy could require a correction rather than the ‘correction requested but not granted’ note as offered by INZ in

³⁷ Privacy Act 2020. s 22(7)(4) Information privacy principles

³⁸ *Jones v Waitemata District Health Board*;[2015] NZHRRT 52 at [38]

³⁹ *Henderson v Commissioner of Inland Revenue* [2004] NZHRRT 27 at [58]

this case. Given the essential role a birth date plays in everyday interactions and in accessing legal entitlements reliant on age, the Commissioner found that the same argument applied in this case as in *Henderson*. The consideration of “whether anything turns on the accuracy of their records” was raised in *Plumtree v Attorney General*⁴⁰. This was equally applicable in the case raised by the complainant for the same reasons as previously applied regarding the central role a date of birth plays in the access to appropriate services and rights. INZ still refused to change the date of birth and the case was referred to the Human Rights Review Tribunal. While the result of the refusal to correct information had the impact on the claimant of not allowing him to access legal entitlements, such as obtaining a drivers license, it is also a concern that INZ provides information to the Migration Five and was in this case providing probable false information.

Waikato District Health Board (DHB): In May 2021 Waikato DHB was impacted by a ransomware attack which resulted in the DHB having to disconnect totally from the internet to prevent further compromise. This resulted in a huge impact on the delivery of Healthcare services for several months. Prior to this event, Waikato DHB had been warned that its IT security was inadequate⁴¹. The exact impact and the point of entry of the attack is difficult to pinpoint as information provided by Te Whatu Ora is heavily redacted and the DHB made the decision to not publicly release the findings from the review into the attack.^{42 43}.

⁴⁰ *Plumtree v Attorney General* [2002] NZHRRT 10 at [145].

⁴¹ Natalie Akoorie ‘Waikato DHB warned a cyberattack ‘catastrophic for patient safety’

⁴² Waikato District Health Board (WDHB) Incident Response Analysis Final Report 2)

⁴³ Nikki Preston “Waikato DHB cyber attack: Hospital bosses fearful of copycat attacks and tipping hackers off”

Media reports state that when ransom demands failed a link to the stolen dataset was sent out to media and uploaded to the dark web⁴⁴. This data set was reported to contain information for approximately 4000 individuals - patients and staff of Waikato DHB.⁴⁵

Data security measures in place and the use of threat intelligence platforms within Government entities.

The National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) is part of the Government Communications Security Bureau (GCISO) Te Tira Tiaki. The GCISO is one of the main agencies sharing data under the Five Eyes alliance, along with the Directorate of Defense Intelligence and Security and the New Zealand Security Intelligence Service. One of the roles of the GCISO is to provide high-grade encryption products and support to Government agencies and to “utilize performance controls to support prioritization of digital investment to lift information security across government”.⁴⁶ The NCSC tends to work with New Zealand Government agencies with higher threat intelligence and protection platforms. They provide three main services related to threat security platforms. Communication Security to protect highly sensitive data through encryption is not a day-to-day requirement for most parts of the majority of government agencies but is essential for Government agencies when utilising the classification above the level of RESTRICTED. This certainly applies

⁴⁴ “Waikato DHB Privacy Breach” -article by Lane Neave (21 December 2021)

⁴⁵ Lane Neave

⁴⁶ GCISO role and responsibilities

to a number of the New Zealand Agencies who would provide information to the key agencies under the 'Five Eyes' Alliance. NCSC also provide cyber threat detection and disruption capabilities to counter advanced malware to a number of what are regarded as 'nationally significant government agencies' through the cyber defence capability product CORTEX. One measure of its apparent success is that the program allows GCSB to detect, on average, 7 cyber intrusions affecting one or more New Zealand organisations in a typical month. GCSB states that in a typical month roughly 0.5% of internet traffic analysed has a signature of advanced malware associated with it⁴⁷. While this may seem a small amount the experience with the Waikato DHB has shown what issues a single event can result in. NSCS has developed its own more commercial threat Intelligence Platform, a service called Malware Free Networks. It is available to organisations outside the nationally significant agencies and is available to small to medium enterprises, large corporates, as well as government organisations. One of the major points of MFN is it allows clients to telemetry information back to NCSC to help improve knowledge of threats targeting New Zealand organisations. The organisations can access the MFN service through their network operator or primary cyber security service provider. One NZ announced in July 2023 that they were rolling out MFN on the broadband and mobile networks, which has technically moved the level of protection to domestic users as well as business⁴⁸.

When examining a government agency which one would expect to utilize threat intelligence platforms in view of past breaches, one might look at the Ministry of Social

⁴⁷ GCISO – information on Cyber Threats disclosed in a speech to Transparency International New Zealand

⁴⁸ One New Zealand Media Release 15 May 2023

Development (MSD). MSD is one of five foundation agencies for the Data Protection and Use Policy endorsed by Cabinet in 2019⁴⁹. According to the Annual Report 2019-2020 the Ministry of Social Development *“have taken significant steps towards implementing a privacy- and security-by-design approach to the way we look after the information we hold. Our information privacy and security teams work with project teams throughout the organisation to ensure that risks are identified and mitigated as early as possible.”*

*“have taken significant steps towards implementing a privacy- and security-by-design approach to the way we look after the information we hold. Our information privacy and security teams work with project teams throughout the organisation to ensure that risks are identified and mitigated as early as possible”*⁵⁰ Subsequent annual reports state that their business risk management policy having been reviewed to ensure that it is fit for purpose, accessible and supports MSD staff to apply risk management to their day-to-day activities. They do not provide details of whether they have a threat intelligence platform in use but may regard this information commercially sensitive. They may however make use of the MFN or CORTEX programs.

Conclusions

From examining the privacy breaches experienced within New Zealand Government agencies it is apparent that the use of threat intelligence platforms performs a valuable role in preventing large scale events the majority of privacy breaches are the result of

⁴⁹ Data Protection and Use Policy (DPUP) was developed by the Social Wellbeing Agency to provide a shared set of rules for respectful, trusted and transparent use of personal information.. Foundation agencies in 2019 were Ministry of Social Development, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Health, Oranga Tamariki and the Social Wellbeing Agency .

⁵⁰ Ministry of Social Development “Annual Report 2019-2020”

staff error and this is an area that needs to be consistently examined and staff education regarding data security needs to be mandatory.

2.4 Case Studies within ‘Five Eyes’ Alliance Nations:

2.4.1 Australia

Australia faces a complex and evolving landscape of cyber threats, with personal information often at the forefront of cybercriminals' targets. Notably, the country has experienced a concerning trend where data breaches within government agencies are predominantly linked to human error rather than intentional malicious attacks.

In a revealing snapshot of this vulnerability, a report in 2016 highlighted that out of 34 data breaches reported by Australian Government agencies over a six-month period, 25 were attributed to human error. This underscores a critical aspect of cybersecurity challenges in the country, emphasizing that a substantial number of breaches occur due to unintentional mistakes rather than orchestrated cyberattacks⁵¹.

Human error manifests in various forms, with incidents ranging from the accidental release or publication of sensitive data to instances where private information is mistakenly sent to the wrong recipient. These errors, while unintended, expose individuals' personal information to potential risks and compromise the integrity of data held by government agencies.

While Australia, like many other nations, is not immune to deliberate cyber threats, the prevalence of human error highlights the importance of comprehensive cybersecurity

⁵¹ Judy Skatssoon “Government agencies report 34 data breaches”

education and training programs. Ensuring that individuals within government agencies are well-versed in cybersecurity best practices can significantly mitigate the risk of data breaches resulting from inadvertent mistakes.

In addition to addressing human error, the broader cybersecurity landscape in Australia requires continuous vigilance against intentional cyber threats. Malicious actors often exploit vulnerabilities in systems, and the protection of personal information demands robust defenses. Collaborative efforts between government bodies, private organizations, and cybersecurity experts are paramount to staying ahead of evolving cyber threats.

Australia's commitment to fortifying its cybersecurity infrastructure, reducing human error, and proactively countering intentional cyber threats is crucial for maintaining the trust of its citizens and securing sensitive personal information. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, a proactive and adaptive approach to cybersecurity remains essential for safeguarding Australia's digital future.

2.4.2 Canada.

Canada, like many nations, has found itself at the intersection of technological advancements and the ever-growing threats in cyberspace. Recent incidents, such as the credential stuffing attack on the Canada Revenue Agency (CRA), cyberattacks on the Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP), and the breach of the National Security and Intelligence Review Agency (NSIRA), underscore the complexity of cybersecurity challenges facing the country.

In July 2020, the CRA fell victim to a credential stuffing attack, a type of cyber assault where login credentials obtained from a previous data breach are used to gain unauthorized

access to unrelated services. This incident raised significant concerns as approximately 13,000 Canadians were impacted^{52 53}. The attackers leveraged stolen credentials to compromise user accounts, highlighting the importance of robust security measures and vigilant monitoring to thwart such attacks.

The CRA incident emphasizes the need for organizations to adopt advanced security measures, including multi-factor authentication and continuous monitoring, to thwart credential stuffing attacks. As cybercriminals evolve their tactics, a proactive approach to cybersecurity becomes paramount, ensuring that potential vulnerabilities are identified and addressed promptly.

The Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP), an agency tasked with upholding law and order, faced cyber threats in October 2019 and July 2020. During these incidents, personal information belonging to RCMP officers was maliciously accessed and misappropriated. The scale of the attack was alarming, with over 260GB of stolen information reported^{54 55}. The breach not only posed a risk to individual officers' privacy but also underscored the broader challenge of safeguarding sensitive data within government entities.

The cyberattacks on the RCMP not only exposed the personal information of officers but also spotlighted the critical role of cybersecurity awareness and training within government

⁵² Malone “A Report Card on the Canadian Federal Government’s Response to Data Breaches”

⁵³ Patel R and Ling P “CRA shuts down online services after thousands of accounts breached in cyberattacks

⁵⁴ Patel R and Ling P.

⁵⁵ Marfo for CTV News “Current and former public service, RCMP, military members affected by data breach, federal government warns”

agencies. Strengthening cybersecurity practices at both the organizational and individual levels is crucial to mitigate risks and respond effectively to evolving threats.

In March 2021, the NSIRA, a crucial independent government agency responsible for reviewing all national security and intelligence activities conducted by the Government of Canada, experienced an "unauthorized access" incident. During this breach, two files containing configurations for a server and an active directory database were stolen. The implications of such a breach are profound, as it involves sensitive information related to national security activities. The incident prompts a need for a reevaluation of cybersecurity protocols within agencies entrusted with critical national functions.⁵⁶

The NSIRA breach raises concerns about the resilience of government agencies responsible for national security oversight. The theft of server configurations and active directory data underscores the need for enhanced cybersecurity frameworks, regular audits, and rapid incident response mechanisms to protect sensitive information integral to national security.

2.4.3 The United Kingdom

The United Kingdom has become a prominent target in the global landscape of cyber threats, with a myriad of attacks aimed at compromising personal information and critical infrastructure. Among these, the SolarWinds cyberattack and incidents targeting the National Health Service (NHS) stand out as notable examples, highlighting the evolving challenges faced by the UK in the realm of cybersecurity.

⁵⁶ NSIRA's update concerning the recent cyber event – continuing notification of affected individuals on 16 August 2021.

The SolarWinds cyberattack, a supply chain attack orchestrated by the Russian Foreign Intelligence Service, reverberated beyond U.S. borders, impacting numerous countries, including the UK. Government entities and critical infrastructure, reliant on SolarWinds software, fell victim to this sophisticated attack. The breach exposed the vulnerabilities inherent in the software supply chain, emphasizing the need for robust cybersecurity measures to thwart such intrusions.

Within the UK, the NHS has been a recurrent target of cyber threats, with attacks escalating in frequency and sophistication. The healthcare sector holds a treasure trove of sensitive personal information, making it an attractive target for cybercriminals. The WannaCry ransomware attack in 2017 stands as a stark reminder of the potential consequences of such breaches. This attack paralyzed NHS computer systems, affecting patient care and highlighting the vulnerability of critical infrastructure to cyber threats.

The NHS, in its role as the guardian of health-related personal data, faces persistent challenges in fortifying its defenses against cyber threats. The SolarWinds incident served as a global wake-up call, prompting a reassessment of cybersecurity strategies to safeguard against supply chain vulnerabilities.

As the UK continues to grapple with the dynamic and evolving nature of cyber threats, there is a pressing need for collaboration between government agencies, private entities, and international partners. Information sharing, proactive threat detection, and robust cybersecurity frameworks are essential components of a resilient defense against cyber threats. Moreover, public awareness and education about cybersecurity best practices contribute to creating a more secure digital environment.

In conclusion, the UK's experience with cyber threats underscores the urgency of prioritizing cybersecurity measures to protect personal information and critical infrastructure. The SolarWinds cyberattack and NHS incidents serve as cautionary tales, emphasizing the imperative for a comprehensive and collaborative approach to cybersecurity in the digital age. The ongoing commitment to adapt and innovate in the face of evolving cyber threats remains pivotal in securing the nation's digital landscape and the privacy of its citizens.

2.4.4 USA

SolarWinds Cyberattack:

The SolarWinds cyberattack, also known as the 2020 US cyber-attack, marked a significant and audacious assault on the cybersecurity infrastructure of the United States. This sophisticated attack, executed as a supply chain attack, exposed vulnerabilities in the software supply chain and had far-reaching implications, affecting not only SolarWinds but also major U.S. federal agencies and international entities..

Supply Chain Dynamics and the SolarWinds Compromise:

SolarWinds, a Texas-based network management software company, played a pivotal role in the cyber incident. Its software, particularly the widely used Orion platform, was embedded in various U.S. federal government systems to monitor network activity. However, the attackers, identified as the Russian Foreign Intelligence Service⁵⁷ leveraged a supply chain attack methodology. This form of cyberattack involves infiltrating an organization's suppliers to gain unauthorized access to the target's systems or data.

⁵⁷ GAO – SolarWinds Cyberattack Demands Significant Federal and Private-sector Response

In February 2020, threat actors planted a remote access tool malware within a file that eventually found its way into SolarWinds' Orion software updates. This 'trojanised' code served as a backdoor, allowing the attackers remote access to any system where the compromised update was installed. SolarWinds estimated that approximately 18,000 of its customers received the compromised software update ⁵⁸. However, the attackers selectively exploited this breach, focusing on a smaller subset of high-value customers, including critical U.S. federal agencies.

Impact on U.S. Federal Agencies:

The SolarWinds cyberattack had profound implications for several U.S. federal agencies, revealing the extent of the breach's sophistication and strategic intent. Among the agencies affected were the U.S. Treasury, Commerce Department, Department of Homeland Security, Department of Justice, Department of State, and the Administrative Office of the United States Courts. The breach raised concerns about potential espionage, with the stolen information possibly intended for use in subsequent attacks on more secure agencies like the CIA and NSA⁵⁹

Beyond U.S. Borders: International Ramifications

The SolarWinds cyberattack extended beyond U.S. borders, reaching international clients of SolarWinds, including government entities. In the United Kingdom, government clients such as the Home Office and the National Health Service fell victim to the attack. The European Parliament also faced the brunt of this cyber onslaught. The global nature of the

⁵⁸ Sanger, David E.; Perloth, Nicole; Schmitt, Eric "Scope of Russian Hack Becomes Clear: Multiple U.S. Agencies Were Hit"

⁵⁹ Sanger, David

attack highlighted the interconnectedness of cybersecurity threats, emphasizing the need for international cooperation in addressing such incidents.⁶⁰

Department of Homeland Security (DHS) Involvement: A Repeated Target:

The Department of Homeland Security (DHS), a critical component of the U.S. government responsible for safeguarding the nation's security, found itself entangled in the web of cyber threats, adding another layer of complexity to the SolarWinds incident.

In 2017, a former DHS employee, part of an ongoing criminal investigation, was discovered to be in possession of personally identified information belonging to 250,000 DHS employees and individuals involved in ongoing criminal investigations, including witnesses. Unlike the SolarWinds attack, this data was not stolen through a cyberattack, and it did not surface on the dark web. Instead, it was an internal breach involving an individual with insider knowledge^{61 62}. This was not the first time the DHS faced cybersecurity challenges. In 2016, hackers targeted the DHS, exposing personal information belonging to 20,000 Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) employees. Subsequently, the details of almost 10,000 DHS employees were also compromised. The attackers, in this instance, exploited vulnerabilities in a Department of Justice Database, underscoring the interconnected vulnerabilities across federal agencies.⁶³

⁶⁰ Sanger, David.

⁶¹ Data leak Lawyers “When 246,000 U.S. Department of Homeland Security Employees’ details are found on a home computer, it’s time to question data security”

⁶² Trend Micro “Data Breach Compromised 250,000 PII of U.S. Department of Homeland Security Employees, Witnesses”

⁶³ Silverstein “Hacker publishes contact info for 20,000 FBI employees, one day after massive Department of Homeland Security data dump”

Lessons Learned and Ongoing Challenges:

The SolarWinds cyberattack underscored the ever-evolving nature of cyber threats and the need for continuous adaptation in cybersecurity strategies. It exposed the vulnerabilities present in the software supply chain and the potential for adversaries to exploit trusted suppliers to infiltrate targeted systems. The incident also highlighted the interconnectedness of international cybersecurity, emphasizing the importance of global cooperation in addressing such threats.

As the U.S. and its allies grapple with the aftermath of the SolarWinds attack, lessons learned include the imperative for more robust supply chain security measures, enhanced threat detection capabilities, and the necessity of international collaboration in addressing cyber threats. Ongoing challenges involve fortifying critical infrastructure against future attacks, refining incident response strategies, and staying ahead of the evolving tactics of sophisticated threat actors.

In conclusion, the SolarWinds cyberattack was a wake-up call for governments, organizations, and cybersecurity professionals worldwide. It demonstrated the need for heightened vigilance, collaboration, and innovation in the face of an ever-expanding and interconnected digital threat landscape. Addressing the aftermath of such cyber incidents requires a collective and adaptive approach to secure the digital future of nations and organizations alike.

CHAPTER 3

CRITICAL ANALYSIS

Critique of Privacy Laws Relating to Personal Information: Australia, Canada, New Zealand, United Kingdom, and United States

The privacy laws discussed for Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States demonstrate varying strengths and weaknesses in their approaches to protecting personal information. While each country has made efforts to address the challenges of the digital age, there are notable disparities that warrant examination.

Strengths:

Australia:

The Privacy Act 1988 and Australian Privacy Principles (APPs) establish a comprehensive framework, emphasizing transparency and the responsible handling of personal information. The Notifiable Data Breaches (NDB) scheme adds a layer of proactive transparency, ensuring timely notifications in the event of a data breach. The My Health Records Act 2012 and the Telecommunications (Interception and Access) Act 1979 reflect a sector-specific focus, acknowledging the unique privacy considerations in healthcare and telecommunications.

Canada:

PIPEDA provides a foundational framework for privacy protection in the private sector, emphasizing fairness, transparency, and accountability. The Digital Privacy Act enhances PIPEDA by introducing mandatory breach reporting, bolstering transparency in the face of

data breaches. Sector-specific legislation, such as PHIPA, recognizes the need for tailored privacy regulations in specific industries.

New Zealand:

The Privacy Act 2020 introduces clear principles, addressing lawful purpose, storage and security, access and correction, and agency disclosure. The Notifiable Data Breaches requirement demonstrates a commitment to proactive transparency and accountability. The Health Information Privacy Code recognizes the sensitivity of health-related data, providing additional safeguards.

The United Kingdom:

The GDPR, a pivotal regulation, sets high standards for data protection, emphasizing transparency, fairness, and individual rights. The Data Protection Act 2018 complements GDPR, providing additional provisions and clarifications, especially in areas not covered by GDPR. The Privacy and Electronic Communications Regulations (PECR) address specific privacy concerns related to electronic communications.

The United States:

The Privacy Act of 1974 was a historical foundation, recognizing the importance of limiting government collection and handling of personal information. Sector-specific regulations like HIPAA and GLBA provide targeted protections for health and financial data. State-level initiatives, like CCPA and VCDPA, indicate a willingness to address privacy concerns despite the lack of federal legislation.

Weaknesses:

Australia:

While the legislative framework is robust, the efficacy of enforcement mechanisms and penalties for non-compliance could be more clearly defined. The fast-paced evolution of technology is not explicitly addressed, and the framework may struggle to keep up with emerging risks like artificial intelligence and cross-border data flows.

Canada

The absence of a dedicated constitutional provision for privacy, akin to the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms, leaves a potential gap in the legal foundation for privacy rights. Again, the challenges posed by emerging technologies and the extraterritorial nature of data flows require ongoing adaptation that might be difficult to achieve given the complexities of global interconnectedness.

New Zealand:

Similar to Australia, the rapid evolution of technology is not explicitly considered, potentially leaving gaps in addressing emerging risks. The global nature of data flows and international standards could present challenges that need careful consideration.

United Kingdom:

The challenges posed by emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, raise questions about the ethical use of personal data and require ongoing adaptation. The implications of Brexit have introduced complexities in aligning privacy standards with international expectations.

The United States:

The absence of a comprehensive federal privacy law results in a fragmented landscape, with varying standards across states and sectors. The Privacy Act's limitations in scope, technological relevance, and individual rights underscore the need for a more modernized

framework. Ongoing challenges in crafting federal legislation, especially in reconciling divergent views and balancing innovation with privacy, highlight the complexities of the U.S. privacy landscape.

Overall Critique:

While all the discussed countries demonstrate commitment to privacy protection, there are common weaknesses that transcend borders. The rapid pace of technological advancements, the need for global alignment, and the challenge of balancing innovation with privacy consistently emerge as areas requiring attention. Furthermore, the absence of a comprehensive federal privacy law in the United States stands out as a notable gap, contributing to a fragmented and inconsistent approach to privacy protection. Moving forward, all nations must prioritize ongoing adaptation, global collaboration, and the crafting of modern, comprehensive frameworks to address the complexities of the digital age and safeguard individuals' privacy rights effectively.

Overarching Trends seen:

Ransomware Attacks on Government Agencies: Both in New Zealand (Mercury IT attack) and within the Five Eyes alliance countries (SolarWinds attack in the USA), ransomware attacks have been prevalent. These attacks, often targeting third-party IT support providers or exploiting vulnerabilities in software supply chains, have significant implications for the affected agencies.

Human Error as a Common Cause: Privacy breaches within government agencies are frequently attributed to human error. Data entry mistakes, sharing sensitive information via

emails, and improper handling of information have been observed in multiple cases, emphasizing the need for consistent staff education and training in data security.

Supply Chain Vulnerabilities: The SolarWinds cyberattack demonstrated the vulnerabilities in the software supply chain. Adversaries leveraged a supply chain attack methodology, infiltrating a trusted supplier to gain unauthorized access to target systems. This highlights the importance of securing the entire supply chain to prevent such sophisticated attacks.

International Ramifications: Cybersecurity incidents, such as the SolarWinds attack, have international repercussions. The interconnectedness of digital systems and the global nature of cyber threats necessitate international cooperation to address and mitigate the impact of such incidents.

Privacy Breaches in Healthcare: Healthcare organizations, such as the Waikato District Health Board and the NHS, have been targeted, resulting in disruptions to healthcare services. The impact on the delivery of healthcare services due to cyberattacks poses a significant concern, highlighting the vulnerability of critical infrastructure.

Root Causes:

Inadequate IT Security Measures: Instances like the Waikato DHB's ransomware attack underscores the consequences of inadequate IT security measures. Warnings about insufficient security were issued prior to the attack, indicating the importance of proactive security measures to prevent such incidents.

Data Entry Errors and Permissions Mismanagement: Human errors, including data entry mistakes and mismanagement of user permissions, have been root causes of privacy

breaches. This suggests a need for robust data governance practices and regular audits to ensure accuracy and prevent unauthorized access.

Lack of Attention to Privacy in Program Development: Reports on the Ministry of Social Development (MSD) storing data in a Government Shared Workspace revealed lapses in attention to privacy during program development. Late completion of impact assessments and errors in user permissions allocation contributed to privacy breaches.

Supply Chain Exploitation: The SolarWinds attack highlighted the risk of supply chain exploitation. The attackers successfully compromised a trusted supplier to gain access to target systems. This calls for enhanced scrutiny and security measures across the entire supply chain.

Patterns:

Delayed Detection and Response: In multiple cases, including the Waikato DHB's ransomware attack and the Stats NZ breaches, there were delays in detecting and responding to incidents. Timely detection is crucial to minimizing the impact of cyberattacks, and agencies need robust incident response mechanisms.

Insider Threats: the insider threat at the Department of Homeland Security (DHS), and the case of the MSD's inadvertent data sharing due to permissions mismanagement, highlight the risks posed by insider threats. Organizations need mechanisms to identify and mitigate insider risks.

Insufficient Privacy Safeguards: In various instances, breaches were attributed to insufficient privacy safeguards, such as researchers sharing images from databases or

breaches occurring due to policy violations. Strengthening privacy safeguards, including education and adherence to policies, is critical.

Need for International Collaboration: Cybersecurity incidents, especially those with international ramifications like the SolarWinds attack, underscore the need for enhanced international collaboration in sharing threat intelligence and developing strategies to address evolving cyber threats.

Recommendations:

Enhanced Security Measures: Government agencies need to implement and continuously update robust security measures, including threat intelligence platforms and encryption technologies, to safeguard against cyber threats.

Staff Training and Education: Regular and mandatory staff training programs on data security and privacy are crucial to mitigate the risks associated with human error, such as data entry mistakes and inadvertent sharing of sensitive information.

Supply Chain Security: Organizations should prioritize securing the entire supply chain, including stringent vetting of third-party suppliers and continuous monitoring to detect any anomalies or suspicious activities.

Proactive Privacy Oversight: Agencies must incorporate privacy considerations into the development of programs and conduct regular privacy impact assessments. Proactive oversight can prevent privacy breaches resulting from data mishandling.

Timely Incident Response: Establishing and regularly testing incident response plans is essential for timely detection and response to cyber incidents. Delays in response can exacerbate the impact of breaches.

International Cooperation: Given the global nature of cyber threats, fostering international collaboration is imperative. Sharing threat intelligence and best practices among nations can strengthen collective defenses against cyber adversaries.

These recommendations, if implemented comprehensively, can contribute to building more resilient and secure government systems in the face of evolving cyber threats.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION

This thesis explores the protection of personal information under the electronic record management strategies and processes of New Zealand Government Ministries as governed by the Privacy Act 2020 from the perspective of New Zealand within the ‘Five Eyes’ Alliance, specifically focusing on immigration-related data shared among member states. Legislative frameworks, case studies, and emerging technologies were considered to provide a comprehensive analysis of the complexities surrounding digital sovereignty and privacy while complying with the information sharing arrangement. A critical examination of the most relevant, recent, and scholarly materials was carried using key search terms to allow a comparative analysis of the relevant legislation in each of the alliance member States. This research identified gaps in the current understanding of data security measures within associated Government Ministries and within associated agencies within the alliance.

4.1 Summary of Findings

While attacks on data security continue and will likely always continue there are consistently being improvements in threat protection platforms to address current threats and address future threats. Government agencies need to implement and continuously update robust security measures, including threat intelligence platforms and encryption technologies, to safeguard against cyber threats. Where cyber-attacks have not been

prevented robust incident response mechanisms need to be in place to reduce the impact of the attack.

Personal information needs to be stored securely and only retained for as long as it is necessary in order to be used for its primary purpose. The risk when this is not followed through with was shown in a number of the major cyber attacks on government agencies where person information belonging to past employees was stolen by the threat actor.

The requirement for unique identifiers related only to a single organisation as required under IPP 13 of the Privacy Act 2020 vs the single unique identifier, the Social Security number, used in the United States has the potential to reduce the risk of identity theft.

4.2 Recommendations

Given that this analysis took the form of a literature review and there has been no similar research previously carried out, the lack of research into the evaluating data security measures in the 'Five Eyes' Alliance with or without a focus on the Electronic Record Management of any nation's government ministries has not been able to be resolved despite the identification of a number of challenges. It would therefore be the recommendation that research be undertaken, taking advantage of opportunities to request information directly from Government agencies within each country, to provide a full analysis of the similarities and differences between data governance within government agencies within the 'Five Eyes' Alliance nations. Given that we do not have any grasp of what the future information sharing activities between the nations may involve there exists the need for a nuanced understanding of personal information and digital sovereignty in a global context.

A further identified area for research highlighted in the high level of data breaches related to user error would be what level and frequency of training in information security would be sufficient to increase understanding and maintain the ability to recognize and prevent potential breaches while identifying roadblocks to employees engaging or being sufficiently able to focus on risk reduction, for example high workloads, insufficient staffing, delivery at a more technical level than is easily comprehended. There is research available into the positive impact of information security concern awareness on reduction in user error data breaches^{64 65 66 67}

⁶⁴ Williams-Banta, Pauline Elaine. "Security technology and awareness training; do they affect behaviors and thus reduce breaches?."

⁶⁵ Price "Reducing the Risk of a Data Breach Using Effective Compliance Programs"

⁶⁶ Ayereby, Manouan Pierre-Marius. "Overcoming data breaches and human factors in minimizing threats to cyber-security ecosystems."

⁶⁷ Zimmerman "Moving from a 'human-as-problem' to a 'human-as-solution' cybersecurity mindset."

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